

Publication describing the application of current causal inference tools to a representative use-case

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The full paper is available in the MLFPM Data Repository.

Towards effect estimation of Covid-19 non-pharmaceutical interventions

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Abstract

In response to the outbreak of the Covid-19 pandemic, governments worldwide have introduced multiple restriction policies, known as non-pharmaceutical interventions (NPIs). However, there still remains uncertainty about the relative impact of such policies. In this work, we quantitatively assess the effectiveness of NPIs using a causal inference approach. We gather geospatial data to study the effect size of different NPIs as measured by change of the reproduction number and mobility trends. Our analysis includes the most frequent NPIs that were applied by 121 countries throughout 2020 until February 2021 as well as country-level information such as mobility and economic, demographic, environmental, social and health indicators. We present findings about the causal impact of five restriction policies - mask wearing, entertainment closure, freedom of movement (border closures), domestic flight restrictions and school closure - and discuss challenges in drawing causal inferences when aggregating multiple countries.

I. INTRODUCTION

With the ongoing Covid-19 pandemic, information on the causal contribution and effect of non-pharmaceutical interventions (NPIs) imposed in the population is critical to inform future preparedness response plans. However, because most countries have implemented multiple restriction measures simultaneously, it is challenging to determine the relative benefit of each. To disentangle the effects of individual NPIs, we need to leverage data from multiple countries with diverse sets of interventions in place. However, even with diverse data from many countries, estimating NPI effects remains a challenging task. First, models are based on epidemiological parameters that are only known with uncertainty, due to many mild or asymptomatic cases that make it difficult to estimate timing of onset of symptoms and serial interval distributions. Second, the data on confirmed cases are generally unreliable as a result of changes in availability of testing within and across countries. Third, the data are retrospective and observational, meaning that unobserved factors could confound the results. Additionally, NPI effectiveness estimates are highly sensitive to arbitrary modelling decisions under minimised assumptions, and should be carefully validated in order to guide policy decisions.

In this work, we use a causal inference approach to assess the impact of five restriction policies adopted by 121 countries over the course of 2020 until February 1st 2021. As a learning problem, we try two different variables as outcomes in the causal effect estimation and we present two causal analysis. First, we consider the effect on the growth rate of the reproduction number, i.e., the rate by which the pandemic spreads. In the second approach, we analyse how NPIs influence the mobility trends across different categories of places such as retail and recreation, groceries and pharmacies, transit stations and workplaces. The intuition behind the two approaches is that imposed restrictions not only directly influence the spread of Covid-19, but also indirectly affect its spread by changing people's behavior and how they respond to policies. We treat each country on a certain day as a distinct data point and characterize each country with a set of covariates - constant across time - that comprise economic, social, demographic, environmental and public health indicators. Additionally, we use the cumulative number of cases and deaths as well as daily mobility trends in different categories of public spaces as dynamic covariates in the model. We design our causal framework with a time independence assumption, as the estimated average causal effect does not make reference to the time at which the NPI was imposed. In each causal analysis, one restriction policy is used as intervention variable per time. Following the common design of causal inference studies, we analyze two groups at each time: countries on days when NPIs were not imposed and countries during the time of imposed NPIs. The causal effect inference is estimated after accounting for confounding biases and positivity violations in order to obtain valid causal estimates.

As intervention variables, we consider NPIs that were frequently implemented across all countries: entertainment and cultural sector closure, mask wearing, school closure, domestic flight restrictions and freedom of movement (restrictions imposed on citizens of a certain nationality when entering a country different than their nation).

II. RELATED WORK

A growing number of studies have evaluated the link between restriction policies applied in several countries and Covid-19 spread. A major part of them quantified the impact of NPIs on the effective reproduction number R or on

the number of new cases through Bayesian hierarchical models [1]–[4] or a combination of statistical, inference and artificial intelligence tools [5]. Compartmental models in epidemiology have also been explored to fit and predict disease transmission dynamics for the purpose of policy recommendation [6], [7]. More recently, [8]–[11] framed NPIs impact estimation using a causal inference approach.

Overall, previous mathematical modeling suggest that public health interventions had a substantial effect on transmission, but highlight that a combination of interventions are needed in order to draw R below one [2], [5]. Nonetheless, the conclusions regarding the effect of each specific intervention are not unequivocal. For example, [12], [13] point out that restrictions like school closure had a large effect on the reduction of R , while [4], [14] did not find a significant evidence of its impact. In fact, existing evidence for the impact of policies is not consistent in the literature, as NPI effectiveness may vary across countries depending on how policies are locally enforced by their governments. Additionally, in some countries measures like mask wearing and social distancing still remain a voluntary practice, making it challenging to accurately quantify their effects.

While most studies focus on a certain set of policies or on a particular country, some studies are broader in scope. For example, in the early stages of the outbreak, [3] investigated the effect of major interventions across 11 European countries and found that current policy interventions achieve control of the pandemic. Subsequently, [12] extended their model to 41 countries and checked robustness on the reported NPI effectiveness results. [15] analysed the overall effect of interventions and community responses across 158 countries and associated delayed policy responses with large number of Covid-19 cases.

In contrast to previous studies, our work analyses the effect of frequently imposed NPIs in 121 countries. We present a comprehensive study on the causal effect of these NPIs on the spread of Covid-19 (represented by the rate of change in R), as well as on people’s behaviour changes, depicted by mobility measures. We conduct a descriptive analysis on how to adjust for positivity violations, and highlight the current challenges in deducing which NPIs effectively mitigate the spread of Covid-19. As opposed to [11], we did not construct a time-varying treatment model explicitly incorporating time, thus we assume that the effectiveness of one NPI is independent of time and of its implementation date. Although in its most simple form, our causal model makes use of standard causal inference methods for correcting observed biases in order to obtain valid resulting effects with more transparent confidence intervals.

III. METHODS

For each causal analysis, we conduct a series of steps from the observational data obtained from each country until the final measured NPI causal effect. These steps are detailed in the following sections.

A. NPI data collection

A major part of this work focused on designing and evaluating the dataset of NPIs implemented in response to Covid-19. In the early stages of the outbreak, great effort was done to collect restriction policies data through an AI-assisted approach. To this end, we designed and used The Worldwide Non-pharmaceutical Interventions Tracker for Covid-19 (WNTRAC)¹ a comprehensive dataset consisting of over 7,200 NPIs implemented worldwide. The NPI events in this dataset are automatically extracted daily from Wikipedia articles using natural language processing techniques (see Figure 1 for a structured summary of the dataset). In order to ensure accuracy and veracity of the data, each automatically extracted event was manually validated by a human annotator, and further classified into a taxonomy of 16 NPI types. More information about the automated extraction can be found in [16].

WNTRAC is updated periodically, and we use for the analyses described hereby the release from February 22 2021. For our experiments we initially select a subset of the ten most frequently imposed NPIs along 121 countries, which correspond to confinement, entertainment/cultural sector closure, freedom of movement (nationality dependent), mask wearing, domestic flight restrictions, international flight restrictions, introduction of travel quarantine policies, mass gatherings, school closure and work restrictions.

We observe long periods in the duration of adopted NPIs along time (see Appendix A). For example, confinement was registered as imposed on March 2020 in almost all countries and stayed in place for a period of several months. In reality, we know that this status changed along time: governments relaxed strict control measures by gradually reopening businesses and the population behavioral responses are different on the first day of confinement vs three or four months later. When there is no change in the status (either implementation or lifting) of restriction policies for a long period, we cannot be certain regarding their impact anymore, due to gradual changes in behaviour. Therefore, we only include in our analysis the days corresponding to the period of the first two weeks after a change in any of the ten NPIs. Although this criteria results in excluding several days from our dataset, it helps us obtaining more confident effects of the restriction policies. These and other limitations are detailed in the Discussion.

¹<https://covidresponse.res.ibm.com>

Fig. 1: AI-assisted approach to build the Worldwide Non-pharmaceutical Interventions Tracker for COVID-19 (WNTRAC) dataset [16].

B. Additional datasets

Our model uses daily consolidated cumulative confirmed cases and deaths from the World Health Organization (WHO)². In order to account for heterogeneity in terms of socio-economic and health factors within individual countries, we use development indicators compiled from officially recognized international sources. From the WHO World Development Indicators (WDI)³, we select a subset of covariates, including access to electricity, mean annual exposure to air pollution and forest area. We also include country-level health information, when possible segregated by biological sex, ranging from life expectancy at birth, cardiovascular (CVD) mortality rates and cancer or chronic respiratory diseases (CRD). As we have indicators per year, we take the most recent metric available per country. Similar variables were used in recent works [5], [17].

We also include covariates describing population distribution, age-structure and human development index from Our World in Data (OWID)⁴. To avoid producing biased estimates with missing values imputation, we only analyse countries that have data available for at least 90% of the full set of the WDI and OWID variables. By taking the intersection of countries with their respective non-missing features, our initial cohort includes 121 countries and 41 socio-economic and health features. A complete list of countries and variables with their respective statistics used in our experiments is detailed in Appendix A.

C. Reproduction Number Outcome

Quantifying transmissibility during a pandemic is an important step to design and adjust public health responses. The effective reproduction number R_t , defined as the average number of secondary cases generated by a typical primary case at time t , provides feedback on the effectiveness of interventions and on the need to intensify control efforts. The value of R changes throughout an outbreak: if it is below one, the outbreak will eventually decline and die out. However, while R is larger than one, a sustained outbreak is likely. The aim of control interventions, such as NPIs, is to reduce R below the threshold value of 1 and as close to 0 as possible, thus bringing a pandemic under control [18].

In this work we use the rate at which R changes over time (R slope), computed on a 7-day interval, as the outcome of one of our causal models. Compared to the daily amount of confirmed cases, R slope shows a much more smoother and stable signal (Figure 2). In addition, this choice of outcome allows the integration of epidemiological parameters, as the computation of R considers properties of Covid-19, including timing of onset of symptoms and serial interval distribution (the time between the onset of symptoms in a primary case and the onset of symptoms in secondary cases).

Several methods have been proposed in the statistical modelling literature to compute R and the resulting values vary depending on the method and model assumptions. We use the R package EpiEstim developed by [18] and extended by [19], due to its statistically robust analytical estimates and extensive use in the disease epidemiology literature. In brief, the R estimation process is based on the disease incidence time series (reported daily cases) and an estimate of the distribution of serial intervals, while accounting for a range of uncertainties surrounding the incubation period and

²<https://www.who.int/emergencies/diseases/novel-coronavirus-2019/situation-reports>

³<https://databank.worldbank.org/source/world-development-indicators>

⁴<https://ourworldindata.org/>

the delays between symptom onset and reporting. We use a gamma distributed serial interval (mean, 3.0 days [SD, 2.0 days]; constant across periods and derived from previous epidemiological surveys on Covid-19), to estimate R and its 95 % confidence interval on each day via a 7-day moving average.

Since estimating the serial interval distribution may not be possible in the early phase of an outbreak, or may be associated with significant uncertainty as countries still had to establish their documentation practices, we exclude the period before 100 cumulative cases of each country from our dataset. Therefore, for each country, the window of analysis starts on the day the cumulative cases exceeded 100 and ends on February 1st 2021.

D. Mobility Outcome

To understand people’s dynamic behavioral response to restriction policies we obtain Google mobility data⁵. These reports include the per-day change in movement across six different categories of places (groceries, retail, transit stations, workplaces, parks and residential areas), with respect to the median value of the same day of the week during the five-week period January 3 to February 6, 2020. For each category, we smooth weekly patterns by using the 7-days rolling averaged mobility. When mobility measures are missing, linear interpolation of the 7-days rolling averaged mobility are used. Each processed data is used independently in our analysis as covariates of the causal models. In addition, we define the mobility outcome as the mean across “grocery and pharmacy”, “retail and recreation”, “transit stations” and “workplaces” (excluding “parks” and “residential” on the basis of inconsistent trends, see Section IV). We therefore obtain a single daily measure of relative mobility by country per day.

E. Predictive analysis of outcomes and covariate/NPI selection

To analyse how the defined covariates are associated with the outcomes, we train two prediction models using as target variables R rate and the average daily mobility. It is assumed that NPIs can only influence R with a delay of 14 days, whereas their impact on mobility trends are more immediate (people adjust their behavior the day after the NPI imposition). We split the data set into two non-overlapping sets: 70% training, consisting of 3,703 (country, date) pairs and 30% test, resulting in 1,588 (country, date) observations, and trained the classifiers considering a time delay of two weeks for R rate and one day for the average mobility output.

We use the gradient boosted trees algorithm with the XGBoost [20] package. Hyperparameters are tuned with 5-fold cross validation on the train dataset, via a randomized grid search. The TreeExplainer from the SHapley Additive exPlanations (SHAP) [21] package is fit on the test set to estimate the contribution of each feature to the XGBoost model.

Although different methods have been proposed in the literature for deciding what covariates to adjust for when controlling for confounding, all of them require different levels of knowledge regarding the nature of the covariates. If we truly had full knowledge of whether each of the socio-economical and health variables influence both NPI intervention and outcome, we could make decisions about confounder control based on such substantive knowledge. However, we follow a different approach and define the set of covariates as the union of the top-20 contributing features for each XGBoost model’s output, according to their Shapley values. In addition to the top features, we include the ten most frequently imposed NPIs (listed in Appendix E) as covariates of the causal model.

The inspection of NPI data revealed large correlations between NPIs, as expected. Since the majority of them were applied simultaneously (school and entertainment/cultural closure, for example, were mostly imposed after confinement started), disentangling the impact of each individual intervention is challenging. Therefore, we include in our analysis just NPIs that shows up as most informative in the SHAP analysis of the XGBoost models, as well as NPIs that are not statistically associated with each other. This selection criteria resulted in five NPIs that are independently assigned as intervention variables in five different causal models: mandating mask wearing, school closure, entertainment sector (nonessential businesses) closure , domestic flight restrictions and freedom of movement (national border closure for foreign citizens).

F. Framework for causal effect estimation

We frame our causal inference models according to the potential outcomes framework of Neyman-Rubin [22]. In standard problems of causal inference, the causal estimand is described by the array of values depicted in Table I. Here, we consider each of the N units in the study as a pair (country, date). Each unit can be exposed or not to a treatment, here called “active treatment” if a certain NPI is imposed on that country on that day and “no treatment” otherwise. Under the time independence assumption, our model does not make reference to the time at which the NPI was imposed neither does it account for time-varying moderators affected by prior treatments. By using cross-country data, we aim to examine effects through conventional regression analyses and propensity score methods.

⁵<https://www.google.com/covid19/mobility/>

TABLE I: The causal estimand, adapted from [22].

Units (country, date)	Covariates X	Potential outcomes		Unit-level Causal Effects	ATE
		Y_1	Y_0		
1	$X(1)$	$Y_1(1)$	$Y_0(1)$	$Y_1(1) - Y_0(1)$	
\vdots	\vdots	\vdots	\vdots	\vdots	
i	$X(i)$	$Y_1(i)$	$Y_0(i)$	$Y_1(i) - Y_0(i)$	$\frac{1}{N} \sum_i Y_1(i) - Y_0(i)$
\vdots	\vdots	\vdots	\vdots	\vdots	
N	$X(N)$	$Y_1(N)$	$Y_0(N)$	$Y_1(N) - Y_0(N)$	

The column labeled ‘‘Covariates’’ X represents variables that take their values before the treatment assignment. These are the socio-economical and health features, the daily number of confirmed cases and deaths, the mobility trends across six public categories and a set of binary features corresponding to whether other NPIs are imposed or not on that time point.

The columns labeled ‘‘Potential Outcomes’’ present the values of the outcome variable Y for each unit at a particular point in time after the intervention (i.e., R rate or average mobility). We assume that for a unit with features $x \in \mathcal{X}$, and a treatment $a \in \{0, 1\}$, there are two potential outcomes: Y_0 and Y_1 . For each unit we only observe one of the potential outcomes, according to treatment assignment: if $a = 0$ we observe $y = Y_0$, if $a = 1$, we observe $y = Y_1$; this is known as the consistency assumption.

‘‘Unit-Level Causal Effects’’ refers to the collection of individual causal effects, which for the i th unit are typically the difference, $Y_1(i) - Y_0(i)$. The fundamental problem of causal inference is that for any unit in our data we only observe Y_1 or Y_0 , but never both. Therefore, each potential outcome is observable, but we can never observe all of them [23].

Finally, the last column is defined at the level of collections of units. In this work, the quantity to be estimated is the average treatment effect (ATE), defined as $E[Y_1] - E[Y_0]$, where it is assumed that the null hypothesis H_0 is that not imposing any NPIs would result in an ATE=0. In other words, the ATE is the average effect, at the population level, of moving the entire study population from ‘‘no treatment’’ to ‘‘active treatment’’. For each ATE computation, one restriction policy is used as intervention variable per time.

Estimating the ATE from the observed data requires accounting for confounding biases in order to minimize the discrepancy between treatment groups. We use *Inverse Probability Weighting* (IPW) [24], a longstanding popular method that overcomes confounding by weighting individuals by the inverse of their probability of being assigned to their treatment, conditioned on their covariates. Such probability can be obtained parametrically by fitting a model that predicts their assigned treatment. We used a logistic regression model with hyperparameters tuned with 5-fold cross validation via a randomized grid search. Once confounding is adjusted and the weights are computed, we estimate the causal effect as a weighted average of the outcome.

In addition to IPW, we compute causal effects by reweighting samples with *Adversarial Balancing* (AdvBal) [25]. In brief, AdvBal generates sample weights for a source data, such that the resulting weighted data becomes similar to a given target data. By using principles from generative adversarial networks (GANs), AdvBal exploits the power of classifiers for measuring two-sample divergence. We use the implementation of IPW and AdvBal from the causallib package [26].

Lastly, we compute the uncorrected effect on the unweighted data by comparing the outcome between the two treatment groups. Before computing causal estimates, we perform positivity violation adjustments (Appendix B).

G. Evaluation measures and statistical tests

We measure the accuracy of our prediction models using the mean-squared error (MSE) with confidence intervals (CI) computed with 100 bootstrapping iterations. When reported on the testing set, the predicted and true values of the estimates are normalized by subtracting the mean and dividing by the standard deviation of the testing set. We assess the statistical association between two binary variables (NPIs) with a two-sided Fisher exact and Benjamini-Hochberg for multiple testing correction. We bootstrap without replacements a sample set of 1,000 units in 1,000 iterations to calculate the ATE, and we report mean and 95% CI for each NPI effect. P-values less than 0.05 are considered statistically significant.

IV. RESULTS

Our initial cohort included all (country, date) pairs during the year of 2020 until February 1st 2021. Excluding several days, which were dismissed from our analysis if there was no change in NPIs after two weeks, as well as number

Fig. 2: Estimate of the reproduction number R throughout the outbreak in Spain (mean, solid red line and 95% credible interval, shaded area) computed with EpiEstim [19]. The blue line represents R rate, computed on a period of 7 days (ratio between R on the current day and the week before). Incidence curve is the number of daily new confirmed cases reported by the WHO. The imposed NPIs during this period are represented by dashed vertical lines colored by types.

of cumulative confirmed cases less than 100 (see Methods), resulted in a number of observations of 5,291. A list of the country names, covariates, outcomes, and number of NPIs occurrences used in our experiments is detailed in (Appendix A).

We estimated R for all countries on the time window of February 2020 until February 2021. As an example, we show the overall dynamics of the epidemic spread in Spain (Figure 2). We observed that measures were implemented in the beginning of March after the outbreaks, resulting in gradual reduction of R until below 1 during April and May. We see that R continuously exceeded 1 in the beginning of June, together with the rising of incident cases. Enhanced control measures were subsequently implemented.

Government interventions have led to different mobility trends for the populations across the six categories. We found a consistent pattern of a sharp reduction followed by a gradual recovery in mobility in groceries and pharmacies, retail and recreation, transit stations and workplaces (Figure 3a). However, visits to parks and outdoor spaces had a more significant recovery compared to the previous categories. Additionally, the residential category is measured in different units (duration rather than visitors). As people already spend a lot of time at home, changes in residential areas are likely to be smaller. The mean mobility is computed excluding parks and residential areas. When analysed across the 121 countries, it reached its minimum on the 14th of April 2020, with a reduction of 52% from baseline. Mobility then recovered, with an estimated mean reduction on the 23th of December 2020 reaching 7% from baseline (Figure 3b).

A. Mobility and reproduction number rate predictors

By splitting the 5,291 (country, date) pairs into 70% training (3,703 units) and 30% (1,588 units) testing sets, we obtained a MSE of 5.05×10^{-4} [3.25×10^{-4} , 6.84×10^{-4}] and 0.77 [0.43, 1.40] for the predictions of average mobility and R rate, respectively. For each predicted outcome, we examined the top-20 contributing features for their XGBoost models. Figure 4 shows the sorted features by the sum of their SHAP value magnitudes over the test set samples, representing the impact each feature has on the model output.

We observed that both number of confirmed cases and its rate strongly contributed for the mobility prediction, although without a clear direction (Figure 4a). Additionally, our results imply that when schools are closed and airports work under limited capacity, the mobility tends to be lower, as reflected by the negative trend of "school closure", "state of emergency" and "international flight restrictions". Contrarily, the NPI mask wearing showed an opposite association: when masks are mandated, there is an increase in the average mobility. This might sound counter-intuitive at first, but masks are generally mandated everywhere in public where social distancing is not possible, including groceries, pharmacies and workplaces. Additionally, mandating the wearing of masks are intended to reduce the likelihood of infection when people *do* move around and interact. Surprisingly, only one restriction policy - school closure - came up between the top-ten most important features. Overall, we expected to see a larger impact of NPIs on the outcome prediction, as their main goal is to limit mobility and social interactions.

We repeated the SHAP analysis training a new model including the mobility features on different categories (Appendix, Figure A.3). The addition of these features improved the performance of the model significantly (MSE =

Fig. 3: Temporal variations in Google mobility trends, mean and 95% CI across the 121 countries included in the analysis. a) Change in community movement relative to the period before the pandemic. b) Averaged mobility excluding parks and residential areas.

$4.62 \times 10^{-5} [1.98 \times 10^{-5}, 10.01 \times 10^{-5}]$). We found that the strongest predictors were mobility trends (of the day before, as we considered a one-day delay to see an effect on the outcome). Thus, there is a high dependency of mobility from one day to the other.

Similarly, Figure 4b shows the most important features for the prediction of the reproduction rate two weeks after NPIs implementation. The SHAP analysis revealed a clear negative correlation between R, the top feature, and the reproduction rate (R slope). Next on the list is R rate computed two weeks before, which showed mixed impacts on the prediction of current R rate. This can be explained by the large variations in the R time-series throughout the pandemic, which led to persistent oscillations in the estimated transmissibility rate. All mobility metrics appeared in the top important features, but also impacted the output prediction without a clear trend. Also on this list are environmental and health variables that did not seem to have a direct or straightforward influence on reproduction rate, such as prevalence of overweight, male mortality rate, forest area and diabetes prevalence. The only NPI that was included in the top features list was mask wearing. Although its SHAP value magnitude is relatively low, a closer inspection of its point colors indicate that it is positively correlated with reproduction rate: when masks are mandated, it contributes to a high predicted reproduction rate. This association is highly non-intuitive, but somehow acceptable, given that the two are highly correlated (masks are mandated when infections rise).

The co-occurrence matrix for the ten most frequently imposed restriction policies is shown in Figure 5, together with the total number of days that they were active. The values on the heatmap represent the percentage of time that a pair of NPIs stayed in place together. Some NPIs frequently co-occurred, i.e., were partly collinear. For example, confinement occurred simultaneously with almost other restrictions for over 50% of the time, considering all countries throughout 2020 until February 1st 2021. Additionally, domestic flight restriction was the least imposed policy registered in the NPI dataset. Under a high collinearity, individual effectiveness estimates are highly sensitive to variations in the data and model parameters [2]. For example, if two NPIs frequently co-occurred, there may be more certainty about the combined effect than about the two individual effects. Additionally, we observed that most NPIs were highly correlated with each other (Fisher exact test, p -value < 0.05). However, there was no association between mask wearing and entertainment/cultural closure (p -value = 0.490), mask wearing and freedom of movement (p -value = 0.204) and school closure and domestic flight restriction (p -value = 0.938). Thus, we included in our analysis just NPIs that serve as an indication for other NPIs based on the frequency they are imposed together, as well as on the lack of association they have between them.

B. Estimated NPIs effect on mobility and reproduction rate

We estimated the individual effectiveness of each NPI, expressed as a percentage change in mobility and R, after correcting for observed confounding biases and positivity violations in the dataset (Appendix B). As mentioned above, five restriction policies were selected as representatives of a larger set of highly correlated NPIs and their estimated effect corresponds to their set of co-occurring NPIs. We tested and compared two causal inference methods for correcting observed biases: IPW and AdvBal. We used a logistic regression model as the propensity model in both methods. For IPW, hyperparameters were tuned with 5-fold cross validation via a randomized grid search. Additionally, we computed

(a)

(b)

Fig. 4: Top-20 important features by SHAP analysis for mobility outcome (a) and R change (b) predictions. Each point represents a single data sample (country at a date). Point color indicates the corresponding feature value (red=high, blue=low).

Fig. 5: (a) Co-occurrence matrix for the ten most frequently imposed NPIs. Cell values indicate the frequency (%) that NPI i (x-axis) was active given that NPI j (y-axis) was active. (b) Total number of days each NPI was active across all countries.

the uncorrected effect on the unweighted data by comparing the outcome between the two treatment groups. Under this model settings, the mean change in R and the percentage reduction in mobility (with 95% credible interval) associated with each NPI is as follows (Table III and Table III, respectively).

TABLE II: ATE estimates of NPIs on R rate with 95% CI.

Method	Freedom of movement	Mask wearing	School closure	Flight Restrictions	Cultural sector closure
IPW	0.023 (-0.238, 0.347)	-0.064 (-1.054, 0.222)	-0.004 (-0.220, 0.244)	-0.047 (-1.208, 0.722)	-0.075 (-0.296, 0.166)
AdvBal	0.083 (-0.197, 0.398)	0.191 (0.029, 0.375)	0.036 (-0.187, 0.273)	0.119 (-0.108, 0.312)	-0.074 (-0.287, 0.139)
Uncorrected	0.089(-0.052,0.238)	0.281 (0.184, 0.388)	0.010 (-0.090, 0.117)	0.080 (-0.035, 0.182)	-0.082 (-0.179, 0.009)

TABLE III: ATE estimates of NPIs on mobility percentage reduction with 95% CI.

Method	Freedom of movement	Mask wearing	School closure	Flight Restrictions	Cultural sector closure
IPW	-2.935 (-12.319, 6.592)	1.652 (-13.557, 20.672)	-1.212 (-12.718, 10.212)	7.260 (-13.004, 18.793)	-2.370 (-14.488, 12.311)
AdvBal	-3.664 (-9.438, 2.960)	4.676 (-0.345, 10.172)	-6.736 (-12.596, -0.774)	4.066 (-3.007, 11.574)	2.544 (-3.907, 9.411)
Uncorrected	-4.194 (-7.058, -0.975)	6.411 (4.087, 8.573)	-9.026 (-11.634, -6.508)	3.166 (0.116, 6.259)	-0.680 (-3.306, 2.105)

We observed two significant results where AdvBal was slightly more determined than IPW: 1) negative effect of school closure on average mobility and 2) mask wearing increasing R rate. The effect of closing schools can be easily interpreted: when schools and daycares are closed, parents do not bring their kids to school. Since they remain at home, there is less movement and mobility is lower. This same association was observed in the SHAP analysis (Figure 4a). The second causal effect must be analysed more carefully. Mask mandates are highly correlated with increased infection (we see more mandates as covid-19 spreading increases). We captured this correlational relationship both in our SHAP analysis of R rate prediction (Figure 4b), as well as in the AdvBal causal effect. However, mask wearing is somewhat an ill defined intervention, as in some countries it still remains a voluntary practice. Given that we can only estimate the effect of "governments require mask-wearing" (rather than "reported mask wearing"), the effect we observe might be entangled with the increased covid-19 spread, making it difficult to be isolated, especially when multiple countries are aggregated. Due to this reason, we assume that this observed effect is statistically insignificant.

For the remaining NPIs, our result imply an overall null effect on both mobility and R rate, as reflected by their overlap of credible intervals on zero.

V. DISCUSSION

We quantitatively assessed the effectiveness of NPIs using a causal inference approach. Using a large set of socio-economical and health variables, documented cases and deaths, as well as information on imposed NPIs, we trained two

models to predict average mobility trends and reproduction rate. Our results show that school closure had a significant association with mobility, as implied by its importance factor in the SHAP analysis for the prediction of percentage in mobility reduction. Additionally, we were able to predict mobility better than the reproduction rate, as the latter is an estimate with a higher degree of uncertainty based on documented daily cases and epidemiological assumptions.

After adjusting for positivity violations in the data, as well as confounding biases with the AdvBal method, the effect of school closures on mobility was significant based on its credible interval. However, our results should be interpreted considering that we simplified the complex dynamics of Covid-19 in a large set of heterogeneous countries evaluated over a period characterized by several waves.

Our study has a couple of limitations. First, our analysis is limited by the type of data utilized and by the need to make simplified modeling assumptions. The number of documented Covid-19 cases implies that documentation practices may have an influence on the results. In particular, definitions and documentation practices differed between countries and over time, especially in the beginning of the pandemic. Short-term fluctuations were considered by taking into account that countries had to develop their documentation practices by starting with at least 100 cases for each country. As to the NPI database, we observe long periods in the duration of adopted NPIs along time. We account for such limitations by taking only the first 14 days after any change in restriction policies, under the assumption that their impact is more certain as soon as they are introduced.

Second, given the heterogeneity of the considered countries (multiple NPIs imposed in different orders and stages of the pandemic), finding causal effects of individual NPIs becomes even more challenging. From a causal inference perspective, treatments are co-occurring and are affecting the outcomes simultaneously. In addition, unobserved factors may also confound the effect of an NPI on the outcome. A previous study using the same data as us showed that effect sizes are more significant when analysed in a single country [27].

Third, we make a strong assumption that the impact of NPIs are time-independent. As a first attempt to apply causal inference to Covid-19 data, we choose to work with cross-country data without making reference to the time at which treatments occur, but rather linking NPI implementation dates to the observed timeline of cases and deaths in a country. In reality, we know that NPI effectiveness may depend on the context of implementation, the presence of other NPIs, country demographics, and specific implementation details. Redesigning our causal analysis taking into account longitudinal data, time-varying treatments, and time-varying moderators is an alternative approach. In addition, our modeling assumptions do not account for any interaction between countries. This simplifying assumption of a common effect reflected our aim to estimate an average effect across all countries.

Given all these facts, the initial results obtained here are somehow not surprising. We did expect to have conclusions coming with caveats, but our results should be seen rather as a learning experiment leading to an open discussion about alternative approaches to make causal inference on Covid-19 NPIs data.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

We studied the effectiveness that NPIs have on mobility trends and on the reproduction rate. Our analysis included five of the most frequent NPIs that were applied by 121 countries throughout 2020 until February 2021, as well as country-level information such as mobility and economic, demographic, environmental, social and health indicators. Guided by the causal model, we examined how the weekly growth rates of the reproduction number are affected by NPIs. In addition, we investigated the impact of restriction policies on changes in the population behaviour, reflected by percentage reductions in mobility metrics. After adjusting for positivity violations and confounding biases in the data, we found an overall reduction of 6.74% (0.77%, 12.6%) in the average mobility when school closure is imposed. Additionally, the other four NPIs considered here (mask wearing, freedom of movement, international flight restrictions and cultural closure) did not cause a significant and clear reduction in reproduction rate or in mobility. Given the mounting evidence that restriction policies can be effective at mitigating and suppressing outbreaks of Covid-19, our results should be interpreted carefully, keeping in mind that our analysis aimed at simplifying the complex overall dynamics of the epidemic spread across a large set of countries.

Our study demonstrates the need for a fine resolution between geographies. Given the heterogeneity of the considered countries and the inter-dependencies between NPIs, finding causal effects of individual policies is very challenging. Additionally, building an appropriate data-driven NPI effectiveness model must be accompanied by extensive validation and sensitivity analysis. Assessing the robustness of our estimates to unobserved confounders and to changes in epidemiological parameters is necessary to ensure that the inferences made are consistent under plausible alternative assumptions. Modelling this difference explicitly is left for future work.

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APPENDIX

A. Frequency of NPI change

The NPI dataset used in this study consists of an AI-assisted algorithm that automatically extracts and collects the imposition of restriction policies from Wikipedia articles using natural language processing techniques. Essentially, the data acquisition on imposed NPIs is more accurate than the information regarding their end date (day when NPIs were lifted). Therefore, we observed long periods in the duration of adopted NPIs along time. We accounted for such limitations by taking only the first 14 days after any change in restriction policies, under the assumption that their impact is more certain as soon as they are introduced.

Fig. A.1: Number of months between any change in NPI across 121 countries until February 1st 2021.

B. Positivity violation adjustment

In order to obtain valid causal estimates, it is necessary to confirm that the positivity assumption is valid in an observational study. Positivity is the assumption that any sample has a positive probability of receiving all values of the treatment variable. In other words, to identify causal effects pertaining to a treatment A, there must be some probability of receiving A given a certain baseline of covariates X, otherwise treatment vs control causal effects cannot be identified. Mathematically,

$$Pr(A = a|X = x) > 0 \text{ for all } x \text{ where } Pr(X = x) \neq 0$$

We can empirically verify to some extent whether positivity holds in a dataset by checking if certain subgroups in the population rarely or never receive some treatments of interest. Specifically, we can inspect if there is some combination of features in a subspace of X for which the probability to be treated is either 1 or 0. If this is the case, inferring the counterfactual outcome for these samples is not possible, as there is no data from one treatment group to infer from. To find violations of positivity in our dataset, we used the methodology described in [28]. By using hierarchical classification models, it is possible to divide the covariate space X into mutually exclusive regions with maximized homogeneity of treatment groups, thus automatically detecting subspaces violating positivity [28]. Here, we trained decision trees classifiers [29] on the covariate space X mapped to a certain NPI used as target variable. For each tree, we found regions in X that were populated by a single treatment group and removed those samples from the dataset. We followed this approach repetitively for each NPI until the we completely characterized the subspaces where possible violations could originate from. Once we ensured treatment groups were comparable, we proceeded to the causal analysis.

Figure A.2 shows a comparison between the AUCs (top) and the propensity distribution (bottom) before and after positivity violation adjustments. From the propensity distribution plot in Figure A.2a we can see that the model was able to discern with almost certainty who was going to receive training and who wasn't. This indicates a problem in positivity, where there are populations we cannot compare because they never had the chance to receive any other treatment from what they actually got. In this case, we need to investigate what is causing the lack of positivity and adjust the data accordingly. Following the method discussed above, we identified those individuals and removed them from the dataset. Figure A.2b shows the the propensity distribution without an observable violation of positivity. The

Fig. A.2: Positivity violation adjustment for mask wearing assigned as treatment. The evaluation plots show comparison of ROCs and propensity scores before (a) and after (b) positivity violation adjustments.

ROC curve exhibits an AUC that is still high but is consistent with the expected value. Importantly, the weighted curve shows that the overall balancing is quite good, since it lies close to the random diagonal line, as required. This analysis was done for the NPI mask wearing as a treatment variable, and similar analyses were done for all other NPIs.

C. Geography selection

The countries were selected based on the availability of reliable NPI data at the time when we started data collection and modelling (April 2020); and for their presence in public datasets such as WHO World Development Indicators (WDI) and Our World in Data (OWID). We excluded countries without any NPI documented. We also excluded very large countries like China and the US, for ease of data collection, as these would require more locally fine-grained data. The final dataset consisted of the following 121 countries:

United Arab Emirates, Afghanistan, Antigua and Barbuda, Angola, Argentina, Austria, Australia, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Barbados, Bangladesh, Belgium, Burkina Faso, Bulgaria, Bahrain, Benin, Bolivia, Brazil, Bahamas, Botswana, Belarus, Belize, Canada, Switzerland, Chile, Cameroon, Colombia, Costa Rica, Cabo Verde, Czechia, Germany, Denmark, Dominican Republic, Ecuador, Estonia, Egypt, Spain, Finland, France, Gabon, United Kingdom, Georgia, Ghana, Greece, Guatemala, Guinea-Bissau, Honduras, Croatia, Haiti, Hungary, Indonesia, Ireland, Israel, India, Iraq, Italy, Jamaica, Jordan, Japan, Kenya, Kyrgyzstan, Cambodia, Republic of Korea, Kuwait, Kazakhstan,

Lebanon, Sri Lanka, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Latvia, Libya, Morocco, Republic of Moldova, North Macedonia, Mali, Myanmar, Mongolia, Malta, Mauritius, Mexico, Malaysia, Nigeria, Netherlands, Norway, Nepal, New Zealand, Oman, Panama, Peru, Papua New Guinea, Philippines, Pakistan, Poland, Portugal, Paraguay, Qatar, Romania, Serbia, Russian Federation, Rwanda, Saudi Arabia, Sweden, Singapore, Slovenia, Slovakia, Senegal, El Salvador, Togo, Thailand, Tajikistan, Turkey, Trinidad and Tobago, United Republic of Tanzania, Ukraine, Uganda, Uruguay, Venezuela, Vietnam, Yemen, South Africa, Zambia, Zimbabwe.

D. Mobility predictors

We examined the top-20 contributing features for the trained XGBoost model on the average mobility outcome, including the six mobility trends that were removed from our first analysis (Figure 4a). We found a high dependency of mobility from one day to the other, reflected by the top mobility features in the SHAP summary (Figure A.3). Note that all features on the list are relative to the previous day of the predicted mobility outcome.

Fig. A.3: Top-20 important features by SHAP analysis for mobility outcome. Each point represents a single data sample (i.e. country at a date). Point color indicates the corresponding feature value (red=high, blue=low); X-axis denotes the effect of the feature on predicted mobility for the sample, which can be positive (increasing mobility predicted score), or negative (decreasing mobility predicted score).

E. Socioeconomic and health variables

TABLE IV: Descriptive statistics for observed vars across 121 countries. For binary variables, we present the proportion (%) and mean \pm standard deviation for non-binary features.

Variable	Mean \pm SD or %	Observations
Socioeconomic vars		
Access to electricity (%)	94.20 \pm 15.19	
Access to electricity, urban (%)	97.84 \pm 6.60	
Forest area (%)	31.07 \pm 20.50	
Air pollution, mean annual exposure	23.85 \pm 18.48	Micrograms per cubic meter
GDP per capita	25984.14 \pm 20784.68	
Current health expenditure	287.75 \pm 1048.12	% of GDP
Human Development Index	0.79 \pm 0.13	
Population	41.44 \pm 94.62	In millions
Population density	287.75 \pm 1048.12	
Median age	34.44 \pm 8.44	
Health vars		
Life expectancy at birth, female	78.39 \pm 6.61	In years
Life expectancy at birth, male	73.14 \pm 6.49	In years
Life expectancy at birth, total	75.72 \pm 6.46	In years
Birth rate, crude	16.14 \pm 7.98	Per 1,000 people
Mortality rate, adult, female	92.07 \pm 62.51	Per 1,000 female adults
Mortality rate, adult, male	157.01 \pm 81.33	Per 1,000 male adults
Mortality rate, infant	12.71 \pm 14.35	Per 1,000 live births
Prevalence of overweight	51.95 \pm 14.28	% of adults
Prevalence of overweight, female	51.06 \pm 12.59	% of female adults
Prevalence of overweight, male	52.72 \pm 17.87	% of male adults
Population ages 60-64, female	4.76 \pm 1.87	% of female population
Population ages 60-64, male	4.48 \pm 1.81	% of male population
Population ages 65 and above	11.91 \pm 6.81	% of total population
Population ages 65 and above, female	7.67 \pm 6.81	% of female population
Population ages 65 and above, male	5.97 \pm 6.81	% of male population
Cause of death, by communicable diseases and maternal, prenatal and nutrition conditions	14.91 \pm 15.18	% of total
Cause of death, by non-communicable diseases	76.98 \pm 17.08	% of total
Diabetes prevalence	7.58 \pm 3.79	% of population ages 20 to 79
Mortality from CVD, cancer, diabetes or CRD, female(%)	13.36 \pm 5.21	Between exact ages 30 and 70
Mortality from CVD, cancer, diabetes or CRD, male (%)	20.15 \pm 7.35	Between exact ages 30 and 70
Mortality rate attributed to household and ambient air pollution	60.92 \pm 59.58	Per 100,000 population
Mortality rate attributed to household and ambient air pollution, male	72.28 \pm 63.46	Age-standardized, per 100,000 male population
Mortality rate attributed to household and ambient air pollution, female	51.55 \pm 57.05	Age-standardized, per 100,000 female population
Mortality rate attributed to unsafe water, unsafe sanitation and lack of hygiene	5.19 \pm 12.48	Per 100,000 population
Mobility		
Retail and recreation	-40.94 \pm 25.48	Restaurants, shopping centers, libraries, and movie theaters.
Grocery and pharmacy	-17.50 \pm 21.26	Grocery markets, drug stores, and pharmacies.
Parks	-16.74 \pm 46.53	Subway, bus, and train stations
Transit stations	-43.66 \pm 23.28	Local parks, public beaches and public gardens.
Workplaces	-33.03 \pm 19.68	
Residential	15.07 \pm 9.29	
NPIs		
Confinement	77.02	
Cultural closure	71.40	
School closure	70.57	
Freedom of movement	78.95	
Domestic flight restrictions	18.79	
Travel quarantine	59.52	
Mask wearing	57.72	
Mass gatherings	46.61	
Work restrictions	40.88	
International flight restrictions	67.21	